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Influence of processing parameters on surface texture homogeneity using Direct Laser Interference Patterning

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ABSTRACT

Surface functionalities in the field of tribology, wettability, biocompatibility and holographic marking introduced by well-defined surface structures strongly depend on the surface texture homogeneity and quality. This work presents strategies for the fabrication of homogeneous periodic surface microstructures employing the Direct Laser Interference Patterning (DLIP) technology with the fundamental transverse mode (TEM₀₀) emitted from a nanosecond laser source. Ti6Al4V substrates are structured using line-like patterns with spatial periods of 7.20 μm , 5.82 μm and 4.31 μm . The impact of various DLIP process parameters such as laser fluence, pulse overlap, hatch distance and spatial period on the produced surface microstructures is introduced and the consequences on the surface texture homogeneity are discussed. Large-area analysis of micro structures is carried out through white light interferometry and scanning electron microscopy. A quantitative measurement scheme of the pattern homogeneity, based on topographical properties such as kurtosis, standard deviation and mean structure height was introduced. Furthermore, the influence of a second modulation arising from the employed hatch distance has been identified. A quantitative parameter, the surface error percentage, has been introduced and employed for the characterization of pattern homogeneity. It was found that specially for larger spatial periods and surfaces treated at high laser fluence, pulse-to-pulse overlaps and a short hatch distance, the overall surface texture homogeneity could be improved up to ~80–90%.

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1. Introduction

Laser texturing is an effective method for the fabrication of surface structures in a single-step process for a large range of applications [1]. In general, microstructures fabricated by direct laser writing (DLW) on metallic surfaces are produced with laser systems having a Gaussian beam shape (TEM₀₀ beam profile). During nanosecond-pulsed laser surface texturing of metals, different thermal effects take place, resulting for instance in recrystallization, melting and/or evaporation of surface material. The ablation behavior of metals typically depends on the processing parameter where large parts of material can be redeposited on the surface due to the recoil pressure of the vaporized phase [2]. This limits the smallest achievable feature sizes and especially the structure quality. Moreover, the lateral resolution of surface features fabricated by DLW is typically limited to about 10–50 μm due to the

wavelength-specific diffraction limit. Thereby, large areas can be processed with limited separation between the produced surface features in the range of 25–250 μm [3–6]. Thus, the fabrication of structures with spatial resolution smaller than 25 μm using nanosecond lasers represents a strong challenge.

On the other hand, the fabrication of repetitive microstructures with separation distances (also called spatial period) smaller than 20 μm are of high interest in a wide range of applications since they provide generally a better performance on different surface functions [7,8]. For example, cell orientation, proliferation and differentiation can be stimulated on biomaterials, especially with feature sizes in the micro- and nanometer scale [9–11]. Another application is related to wettability changes, where the performance of structured surfaces with periodic features below ~20 μm in conjunction with large aspect ratios can prevent ice accumulation [12] which represents a high value particularly for the aerospace industry.

A technique which allows the fabrication of surface periodical structures in the micro and sub-micro range is Direct Laser Interference Patterning (DLIP). This method has been used for a wide range of applications such as antifouling [13], wetting control

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[14–17], tribology [18] electrical conductivity improvement [19] cell adhesion [20] and decorative elements [21]. In addition, DLIP technology has already been used to treat large areas in 2D and 3D parts with periodic micro and nanostructures [22]. The DLIP process is based on the interference process created by overlapping two or more coherent laser beams and thereby producing a periodic variation of the laser intensity. The versatility of the method, in terms of obtainable pattern geometries, has been evaluated by numerical simulations as function of the number of laser beams used, the laser light polarization, intensity and incident angles for each sub-beam [23,24]. Line-like patterns can be created using a two-beam configuration with a controllable spatial period (Λ), which is a function of the laser wavelength λ and the half angle between the two incident beams θ , as described by Eq. (1):

$$\Lambda = \frac{\lambda}{2 \sin(\theta)} \quad (1)$$

As it can be concluded from Eq. (1), the minimal achievable spatial period that can be configured is half of the used laser wavelength. Furthermore, Bieda et al. [25] observed that the structure heights that are obtained when using ns-pulsed laser systems and short spatial periods ($< 3 \mu\text{m}$) are generally limited to a few nanometers for different metals (for example heights of $\sim 35 \text{ nm}$ for a spatial period of $1 \mu\text{m}$ on titanium). In addition, when nanosecond pulses are irradiated on metallic surfaces, the structuring mechanism is based on Marangoni convection, which means that the molten material at the maxima positions flows towards the minima positions, following a surface tension gradient induced by the surface temperature distribution [26,27].

In this work, we demonstrate the fabrication of homogeneous periodic surface microstructures employing a DLIP-2-beam-setup with a Gaussian beam intensity distribution (TEM00) of a nanosecond laser on Ti6Al4V alloy. The nanosecond IR source was selected due to the lower cost compared with ps (or fs) lasers sources. However, the improvement of the structure homogeneity is not related with the pulse duration of the laser source but with the strategy used during the experiments. Thus, the impact of various DLIP process parameters such as laser fluence, pulse overlap and spatial period on the produced surface microstructures is introduced and the consequences on the surface texture homogeneity are discussed. Furthermore, a method for measuring the pattern homogeneity based on different topographical characteristics is proposed which allows the quantitative analysis of the surface pattern quality. The here presented method is of significant relevance to assure in the future a certain performance over the whole treated area as well as to permit in relevant industrial processes to quantitatively describe the produced topography in terms of homogeneity. This is required for instance for quality management.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Flat samples of Ti6Al4V (VSMPO, Russia) were selected for the DLIP laser experiments due to their high range of applications [28]. This alloy is used for instance in the aerospace industry as well as in bio-applications due to its lightness, non-magnetic and biocompatibility properties [29]. The annealed samples have a thickness of 2 mm and an average surface roughness (R_a) of $0.27 \mu\text{m}$, the root mean square (R_q) roughness of $0.29 \mu\text{m}$ and the maximum height of the assessed profile (R_z) of $1.34 \mu\text{m}$. The material's optical reflectivity at 1064 nm is 57% for a normal angle incidence [30].

2.2. Nanosecond Direct Laser Interference Patterning

The laser experiments were conducted on a compact self-developed DLIP system (DLIP- μFAB , Fraunhofer IWS) producing DLIP pixels (irradiated area per pulse which contains the line-like interference pattern) with a diameter of $160 \mu\text{m}$ in the interference area (\emptyset). The fluence was calculated by means of the laser beam radius ($1/e^2$), using the D-squared method [31]. The system is equipped with a Q-switched Nd:YLF laser (Laser-export Tech-1053 Basic), operating at 1053 nm that provides 12 ns pulses at 1 kHz with pulse energies up to $290 \mu\text{J}$, emitting the fundamental transverse mode (TEM00) with a laser beam quality factor of $M^2 < 1.2$. In the DLIP optical head, the main beam is split in two beams using a diffractive optical element (DOE), which are later parallelized by a prism and finally overlapped using a lens with a focal distance of 40 mm. The optical configuration allows the fully automatic control of the spatial period between $1.29 \mu\text{m}$ and $7.20 \mu\text{m}$ by varying the angle of incidence of the beams on the sample, further information about the setup was already published elsewhere [32]. To cover larger areas, the substrates were translated in the vertical (y) and horizontal (x) directions, where the pulse to pulse overlap (y direction) was varied from 90% up to 98.5%. The pulse to pulse overlap (OV) can be calculated as a function of the pulse separation distance p and the beam diameter \emptyset using Eq. (2):

$$OV = \left(1 - \frac{p}{\emptyset}\right) \cdot 100 \quad (2)$$

A schematic representation of the main components in the DLIP system is depicted in Fig. 1(a). The strategy used for the DLIP process is indicated in Fig. 1(b), following the same methodology already reported in [33]. By setting the interference angles θ to 4.23° , 5.24° and 7.09° , spatial periods of $7.20 \mu\text{m}$, $5.82 \mu\text{m}$ and $4.31 \mu\text{m}$ can be calculated using Eq.(1). For the given angles, the variation of the reflectivity is negligible and thus do not influence the structuring process (compared to the normal incidence condition (0°), the variation on the total reflectivity is smaller than 0.3% calculated for non-polarized laser radiation and an incident angle of 7.09° [34], using n (refractive index) and k (extinction coefficient) values of 3.57 and 3.50, respectively [35,36]). The laser experiments were carried out in ambient environment without post treatments.

2.3. Surface characterization

The treated surfaces were characterized using White Light Interferometry (WLI) (LeicaSCAN DCM3D) with a 50 X magnification, with a resolution of 340 nm and 4 nm in the x and y direction, respectively. Using this objective, a total area of $351 \mu\text{m} \times 264 \mu\text{m}$ could be recorded in each measurement. In order to evaluate surface homogeneity, an extended area was measured considering four adjacent areas, resulting in a total area of $702 \mu\text{m} \times 528 \mu\text{m}$, which was significantly larger than the DLIP pixel diameter ($\sim 160 \mu\text{m}$) produced in the interference area. Along the measured area, five individual roughness profiles were taken (perpendicular to the produced line-like patterns) with a length of $550 \mu\text{m}$ each. The extracted profiles were added adjacently, resulting in a sampling length of 2.75 mm. The heights of the profile elements were extracted using the software MountainsMap[®] 7.4 utilizing the step height measurements function. The topographical parameter of kurtosis was determined from the roughness profile according to ISO 4287. Further topographical measurements were carried out using a Scanning Electron Microscopy (Zeiss Supra 40VP) at an operating voltage of 5 kV.

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic representation of the main components in the DLIP system. (b) Strategy used to treat the metallic samples: ϕ , h and p denote the diameter of the interference area, the hatch distance and the pulse separation distance, respectively.

Fig. 2. Scanning electron micrographs of the nanosecond DLIP structures produced on Ti6Al4V using the spatial period $\Lambda = 7.20 \mu\text{m}$, the hatch distance of $43.20 \mu\text{m}$, 90.0% overlap and the fluence values of (a) $F = 1.06 \text{ J/cm}^2$ (b) $F = 1.15 \text{ J/cm}^2$ (c) $F = 1.42 \text{ J/cm}^2$, (d) magnification from the topography in (c).

3. Calculation

3.1. Definition of topographical parameters for homogeneity quantification

Quantification of surfaces using 2D profiles is extensively used in surface engineering for determining for instance the surface roughness, where profile parameters are defined based on the sampling length [37]. The most used parameter to describe surface roughness is the arithmetic mean (R_a) of the absolute heights ($|Z|$) from the mean line of the measured roughness profiles. However, this parameter is susceptible to variations in the surface heights and does not describe the morphology of a topography [38]. For the characterization of the topographical homogeneity of periodic microstructures, it is important to consider the height fluctuations over a certain sampling area. In this work, the height

fluctuations are calculated by 1D extraction of the 2D profiles with the help of the software MountainsMap[®] 7.4. Although an analysis directly from the 3D information is possible [39], this route does not provide a height variation analysis (e.g. it is not possible to calculate standard deviations of the 2D profiles which is fundamental for the approach here presented). Thus, along the microstructure the heights fabricated become in the most relevant variable during the 2D assessment since its changes affect directly the surface texture homogeneity. The mean structure height (R_c) is

$$R_c = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n Zt_i, \quad (3)$$

where Zt are the heights of the i -profile elements and n is the total number of heights considered [37]. The measurement of the data

dispersion can be described by its standard deviation (*Sd*) using Eq. (4) [37,40]:

$$Sd = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (Z_i - \bar{Z})^2}, \quad (4)$$

where \bar{Z} is the mean value of the heights of the *i* – profile elements. Thus, relative error (*Err%*) of a periodic structure in terms of the structure amplitude can be introduced by considering the relation between the terms *Sd* and *Rc* according to Eq. (5):

$$Err\% = 100 \cdot \frac{Sd}{Rc} \quad (5)$$

As a result, the term *Err%* expresses the ratio of height variation to the measured mean height of the profile elements. Furthermore, the topography can be characterized by the kurtosis (*Rku*). For a discrete distribution of heights, *Rku* is defined using Eq. (6) which

relates the mean quartic of the absolute heights ($|Z_i^4|$) and the 4th power of *Rq* (root mean square of the absolute heights) within the sampling length.

$$Rku = \frac{1}{Rq^4} \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |Z_i^4| \right] \quad (6)$$

The kurtosis (*Rku*) characterizes the spread of the height distribution and is connected to the sharpness of the roughness profile. A surface with a Gaussian height distribution has a kurtosis value of three. A spiky surface will have a high kurtosis value (>3) and a bumpy surface a low kurtosis value (<3) [41–43].

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Nanosecond DLIP of Ti6Al4V

In a first approach, the impact of the fluence variation on the microstructure was investigated. Laser parameters were fixed at

Fig. 3. White light interferometry images and typical roughness profiles of the nanosecond DLIP structures produced on Ti6Al4V using the spatial period $\Lambda = 7.20 \mu\text{m}$, the hatch distance of $43.20 \mu\text{m}$, 90.0% overlap and the fluence values of (a) $F = 1.06 \text{ J/cm}^2$ (b) $F = 1.15 \text{ J/cm}^2$ (c) $F = 1.42 \text{ J/cm}^2$.

a pulse-to-pulse overlap value of 90%, the spatial period of $7.20\ \mu\text{m}$ and the hatch distance to $43.20\ \mu\text{m}$. Since arbitrary values could generate irregularities in the DLIP pixel distribution and lead to undefined microstructures, the hatch distance h (or pulse distribution in the x direction) was chosen as a multiple number of the spatial period. In the SEM micrographs depicted in Fig. 2, three different surfaces can be observed which were processed at the laser fluence values of $1.06\ \text{J}/\text{cm}^2$ (Fig. 2(a)), $1.15\ \text{J}/\text{cm}^2$ (Fig. 2(b)) and $1.42\ \text{J}/\text{cm}^2$ (Fig. 2(c)). The initial surface texture of the untreated substrate can still be observed after the structuring process if a low fluence is used (see horizontal features in Fig. 2(a) and (b)). At higher fluence values, the initial surface roughness could be flattened and at the same time structures with higher aspect ratios (height to spatial period ratio) were produced. Furthermore, the high magnification image depicted in Fig. 2(d) clearly shows rede-

position of the molten material which is produced during the laser treatment.

Fig. 3 shows the WLI images of the three surfaces processed at different laser fluences analyzed in Fig. 2. Thereby, examples of aleatory roughness profiles are depicted. The images show the evolution of the height increase as a function of the used laser fluence. For instance, Fig. 3(a) ($F = 1.06\ \text{J}/\text{cm}^2$) reveals a non-homogeneous surface pattern whereas Fig. 3(b) ($F = 1.15\ \text{J}/\text{cm}^2$) and Fig. 3(c) ($F = 1.42\ \text{J}/\text{cm}^2$) highlight line-like patterns with a more defined shape.

The variation of the structure height as function of the laser fluence for the produced line-like patterns with a spatial period of $7.20\ \mu\text{m}$ and a hatch distance of $43.20\ \mu\text{m}$ is shown in Fig. 4(a). Four different overlaps were employed including 90.0%, 96.6%, 98.0% and 98.5% which correspond to 10, 30, 50 and 70 pulses,

Fig. 4. Mean structure heights ($Rc\Lambda$) of produced structures on Ti6Al4V as function of the laser fluence for the spatial periods of (a) $\Lambda = 7.20\ \mu\text{m}$, (c) $\Lambda = 5.82\ \mu\text{m}$ and (e) $\Lambda = 4.31\ \mu\text{m}$ (hatch distances were $43.2\ \mu\text{m}$, $40.74\ \mu\text{m}$ and $43.10\ \mu\text{m}$, respectively). The overlap values of the pulse distribution were 90.0%, 96.6%, 98.0% and 98.5%. The variation of the structure height for the periodic structure (relative error, $Err\ \Lambda\ \%$) are shown for the same spatial periods: (b) $\Lambda = 7.20\ \mu\text{m}$ (d) $\Lambda = 5.82\ \mu\text{m}$ (f) $\Lambda = 4.31\ \mu\text{m}$. The continuous line is just to guide the eye.

respectively. The pulse distribution in the y direction was used to control the overlap of the individual pulses, therefore it indirectly affects the mean structure height produced by DLIP (defined as RcA), calculated using Eq. (3). However, as it can be seen in Fig. 4(a), overlap values over 96.6% did not produce a considerable change in RcA , showing that the structure height remains constant for a certain number of laser pulses.

Using Eq. (5), the relative structure error corresponding to the periodic structure (denoted as $ErrA\%$) was calculated and its variation was correlated with the used laser fluence (see Fig. 4(b)). A reduction of the $ErrA\%$ values could be achieved for laser fluence values higher than 1.15 J/cm^2 combined with overlap values over 90%. This decrease can be attributed to an increase of the RcA value compared to the standard deviation (Sd) (see Eq. (5)) and thus leading to a homogenous roughness profile. The samples treated with fluence values at 1.06 J/cm^2 revealed higher values in the $ErrA\%$ (up to 32%), related with less homogeneous microstructures.

Consistent with the variation of the angle of incidence θ , two additional spatial periods of $5.82 \mu\text{m}$ and $4.31 \mu\text{m}$ were selected for the consequent experiments, using hatch distances of $40.74 \mu\text{m}$ and $43.10 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. These distances correspond to 7 and 10 times the used spatial period, respectively. The used hatch distances were chosen in order to keep them as close as possible to the value of $43.20 \mu\text{m}$ corresponding to the hatch distance used in the first set of experiments (for $\Lambda = 7.20 \mu\text{m}$). The characterized mean height (RcA) values of the produced structures are shown in Fig. 4(c) and (e). In general, it can be observed that smaller heights, in comparison with the structures with $7.2 \mu\text{m}$ period were achieved. This effect has been explained in the past by the different temperature gradients (temperature difference between interference maxima and minima positions over half of the spatial period) that are obtained when varying the spatial period. When a material is irradiated with an interference pattern, the surface is first locally heated at the interference maxima and if the energy is high enough the material is molten (or even ablated). Depending on the pulse duration, the energy located at the interference maxima might have enough time to flow to the colder regions, which are the interference minima positions and the bulk. The distance in which the material is affected thermally can be described by the thermal diffusion length, which is the case of ns pulses and metals varies between 0.5 and $2 \mu\text{m}$ [25]. That means that materials treated with interference patterns with short spatial periods can be also significantly heated at the interference minima positions and thus reducing the thermal gradient. This also reduces Marangoni convection which is characterized a flow of the molten metal from the hot (maxima) to the cooler regions (minima), and thus the obtained structure height is reduced.

As far as the homogeneity is concerned, the outcomes of $ErrA\%$ for the spatial period of $5.82 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 4(d)) are comparable with the fabricated in the spatial period of $7.20 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 4(b)). However, for the surfaces treated with the spatial period of $4.31 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 4(f)), the smallest error was about 15% (for $7.20 \mu\text{m}$ and $5.82 \mu\text{m}$, error values of $\sim 10\%$ were observed). A typical structure obtained for the smallest period is shown in Fig. 5, corresponding to 98.5% overlap, a laser fluence of 1.42 J/cm^2 and a hatch distance of $43.10 \mu\text{m}$. In Fig. 5, it can be seen that even though a mean height (RcA) of $3.36 \mu\text{m}$ was attained, several irregularities are present. The effect involves the decrease in the thermal gradient with the reduction in the spatial period [24], as explained before, as well as possible vaporization of the material which promotes a recoil pressure involving a turbulent flow of the molten material [44,45] and thus reducing the quality of the microstructure.

In addition, to the characteristic periodic microstructure produced by the interference pattern, also a second modulation of the structure topography could be observed for the used hatch distances ($\sim 41 \mu\text{m}$). An example of a typical structure is shown in

Fig. 5. Scanning electron micrograph of nanosecond DLIP treated Ti6Al4V surface using a spatial period $\Lambda = 4.31 \mu\text{m}$, $F = 1.42 \text{ J/cm}^2$, 98.5% overlap and a hatch distance of $43.10 \mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 6, corresponding to a spatial period of $7.20 \mu\text{m}$, with a hatch distance of $43.20 \mu\text{m}$, a laser fluence value of 1.42 J/cm^2 and 96.6% overlap. Although the structure mean height (RcA) obtained was approximately $8 \mu\text{m}$ with an $ErrA\%$ of only $\sim 12\%$, the second modulation is very pronounced. This characteristic topography can be explained by the intensity distribution of the interference patterns that is obtained when two Gaussian beams (TEM00) are overlapped [17,46]. Therefore, the cumulative energy at the center of the interference area is strongly affecting the quantity of molten and ablated material during the movement of the substrate in the y direction, producing the repetitive valleys. In addition, the repetitive length of this modulation was $43.20 \mu\text{m}$, which is clearly related with the hatch distance used in this case. This value was measured using a frequency filter of $8 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter (value higher than the spatial period) during the surface analysis which permitted remove the periodic structure produce by the interference pattern (see inset in Fig. 6). For the evaluation of the topographical homogeneity, the outer limit of the DLIP microstructures (left DLIP area in Fig. 6(a)) was not taken into consideration. An example of the evaluated area by WLI is shown in Fig. 6(b). Hence, for determining the general surface texture homogeneity, this second modulation must be considered. Using the procedure mentioned above, the mean structure height produced by the second modulation (defined as $RcMod$) was also determined.

Fig. 7 shows the mean height of this modulation ($RcMod$) for the spatial periods of $7.20 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 7(a) frequency filter = $8 \mu\text{m}$), $5.82 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 7(c) frequency filter = $6.5 \mu\text{m}$) and $4.31 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 7(e) frequency filter = $5 \mu\text{m}$). The hatch distances were for Fig. 7(a), (c) and (d) $43.20 \mu\text{m}$, $40.74 \mu\text{m}$ and $43.10 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. For each spatial period, the pulse to pulse overlap was varied from 90% to 98.5%. The results show significant differences in the $RcMod$ values depending on the spatial period and fluence values. In the case of the structures produced with the spatial period of $7.20 \mu\text{m}$, $RcMod$ values up to $3.11 \mu\text{m}$ were measured, while for the spatial period of $4.31 \mu\text{m}$ the maximum $RcMod$ was $0.80 \mu\text{m}$ (both cases using an overlap of 98.5% and a laser fluence of 1.42 J/cm^2). In consequence, it can be concluded that a reduction of the spatial period is also related to a less pronounced topography corresponding to the larger modulation ($RcMod$).

In order to better understand the role of the processing parameters, the same analysis was carried out for a significant shorter hatch distance. The results are also presented in Fig. 7, for the same spatial periods ($7.20 \mu\text{m}$, $5.82 \mu\text{m}$ and $4.31 \mu\text{m}$) and hatch distances of $28.80 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 7(b)), $29.10 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 7(d)) and $25.80 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 7(f)). The same laser fluences and overlaps as in the previous case were used.

Fig. 6. (a) Scanning electron micrograph of produced DLIP structures on Ti6Al4V using a spatial period $\Lambda = 7.20 \mu\text{m}$ and a fluence value of $F = 1.42 \text{ J/cm}^2$ at 96.6% overlap. The hatch distance (h) was $43.20 \mu\text{m}$. The inset illustrates the structure height corresponding to the second periodic modulation (R_{cMod}) in function of the hatch distance (h) as well as height of the periodic structure (R_{cA}); (b) confocal microscopy picture of the same area.

Fig. 7. Mean structure height produced by the second modulation (R_{cMod}) of microstructures fabricated on Ti6Al4V using DLIP. The used spatial periods were: $\Lambda = 7.20 \mu\text{m}$ with hatch distances of (a) $43.20 \mu\text{m}$ and (b) $28.80 \mu\text{m}$; $\Lambda = 5.82 \mu\text{m}$ with hatch distances of (c) $40.74 \mu\text{m}$ and (d) $29.10 \mu\text{m}$; and $\Lambda = 4.31 \mu\text{m}$ with hatch distances of (e) $43.10 \mu\text{m}$ and (f) $25.86 \mu\text{m}$. The used pulse to pulse overlaps were 90.0%, 96.6%, 98.0% and 98.5%. The continuous line is just to guide the eye.

The results show that the $RcMod$ height increases with increasing the laser fluence but apparently only for the larger hatch distances ($\sim 42 \mu\text{m}$). For the shorter values ($\sim 28 \mu\text{m}$) no marked trend is visible. Furthermore, comparing the $RcMod$ values for the $7.20 \mu\text{m}$ spatial period for both used hatch distances ($42.2 \mu\text{m}$ for Fig. 6(a) and $28.8 \mu\text{m}$ for Fig. 7(b)) it can be seen that the values for the shorter hatch distance are slightly smaller, especially for higher fluences (e.g. 1.42 J/cm^2). Clearly, smaller $RcMod$ values denote a more homogenous pattern since the second modulation is not pronounced.

For quantitatively determining the surface texture homogeneity of the produced periodic patterns, a comparison between the $RcMod$ (mean height of large modulation) and RcA (mean height of the periodic modulation) was performed. This comparison determines which modulation is predominant. For example,

surface patterns with high RcA and small $RcMod$ denote a very pronounced periodic structure compared to the height of the large modulation. Thus, in this case the patterns will show a better homogeneity. Therefore, this strategy can be used to determine the surface texture homogeneity error of the treated area ($SurfErr\%$) using Eq. (7):

$$SurfErr\% = 100 \cdot \frac{RcMod}{RcA} \quad (7)$$

Using this concept, the variation of the $SurfErr\%$ as a function of the laser fluence, spatial period, pulse to pulse overlap and hatch distance is presented in Fig. 8. The results show that independently of the hatch distance and the pulse to pulse overlap, for low laser fluences (e.g. $\sim 1.05 \text{ J/cm}^2$) higher $SurfErr\%$ are observed (the error bars were estimated using the error propagation method). In

Fig. 8. Surface error ($SurfErr\%$) as function of the laser fluence, hatch distance, overlap and spatial period. Spatial period $\Lambda = 7.20 \mu\text{m}$ with hatch distances of (a) $43.20 \mu\text{m}$ and (b) $28.80 \mu\text{m}$; $\Lambda = 5.82 \mu\text{m}$ with hatch distances of (c) $40.74 \mu\text{m}$ and (d) $29.10 \mu\text{m}$; $\Lambda = 4.31 \mu\text{m}$ with hatch distances of (e) $43.10 \mu\text{m}$ and (f) $25.86 \mu\text{m}$. The used pulse to pulse overlaps were 90.0%, 96.6%, 98.0% and 98.5%. The continuous line is just to guide the eye.

Fig. 9. (a) and (b) Scanning electron micrographs of produced DLIP structures on Ti6Al4V using spatial periods of: (a) $\Lambda = 7.20 \mu\text{m}$ (hatch distance of $28.80 \mu\text{m}$), (b) $\Lambda = 5.82 \mu\text{m}$ (hatch distance of $29.10 \mu\text{m}$), in both cases the laser fluence was $F = 1.42 \text{ J/cm}^2$ at 98.5% overlap, (c) and (d) show its white light interferometry images, respectively.

addition, the calculated *Surf Err%* values increased for large spatial periods (e.g. 87% for $7.20 \mu\text{m}$ and 53% for $4.31 \mu\text{m}$) at the same fluence values. Other characteristic that could be observed is that for shorter hatch distances, better surface texture homogeneity values could be reached, especially for larger periods (see Fig. 8(a) and (b)). The same effect is observed for high laser fluences (for example, surface errors smaller than 20% were measured for 1.42 J/cm^2 and spatial periods of $7.20 \mu\text{m}$).

Two scanning electron micrographs examples of the fabricated periodic microstructures using the spatial period of $7.20 \mu\text{m}$ (with *Surf Err%* = 16%) and $5.82 \mu\text{m}$ (with *Surf Err%* = 10%) are shown in Fig. 9(a) and (b), respectively. In both case, the shortest hatch distances were employed ($28.80 \mu\text{m}$ and $25.86 \mu\text{m}$, respectively). Fig. 9(c) and (d) show the WLI images for each case. As it can be observed in the WLI images, a significant reduction of the second modulation (*RcMod*) could be achieved (compare with the WLI picture in Fig. 6b)).

Finally, as previously stated, the kurtosis (*Rku*) was calculated for all produced surface patterns. As mentioned, this parameter characterizes the spread of the height distribution and is connected with the sharpness of the roughness profile. Fig. 10 shows the outcomes for the spatial periods of $7.20 \mu\text{m}$, $5.82 \mu\text{m}$ and $4.31 \mu\text{m}$ for the different used hatch distances. In general, it was observed that if fluences lower than 1.10 J/cm^2 are used, the measured *Rku* values were higher than 2. In particular, the highest kurtosis was observed for larger periods and large hatch distances (e.g. *Rku* up to ~ 6 in the spatial period of $7.20 \mu\text{m}$ and $43.20 \mu\text{m}$ hatch distance). For higher laser fluences ($F > 1.15 \text{ J/cm}^2$) the kurtosis values were significantly lower (~ 1.5). Furthermore, for the structures fabricated with the smaller hatch distances the dispersion of the *Rku* values was reduced, which means that the obtained characteristic surface morphology do not varies. In addition, a perfect sinus profile has a *Rku* = 1.5, shape that is comparable to the obtained topographies [47]. However, it has to be commented that other profiles might lead to similar results and thus this parameter is insufficient to describe to topography shape.

5. Conclusions

In this work, a strategy for the fabrication of homogeneous microstructures on Ti6Al4V using Direct Laser Interference Patterning with ns-pulsed laser source and a Gaussian beam form (TEM00) was reported. It was shown that homogeneous microstructures can be fabricated on large areas if the hatch distance and the overlap values between successive laser pulses are optimized. A quantitative measurement scheme of the pattern homogeneity based on topographical properties such as standard deviation (*Sd*), mean structure height (*RcA*) and kurtosis (*Rku*) was introduced. Furthermore, the influence of a second produced periodic modulation (*RcMod*) arising from the utilized hatch distance has been identified as the most sensitive parameter during the surface assessment. As quantitative parameter, the surface error percentage (*Surf Err%*) has been introduced and employed for the characterization of the pattern homogeneity.

Based on the observed experimental results, the effect on the different processing parameters on the produced surface textures can be summarized:

- (1) the hatch distance has a relevant importance on the large periodic modulation; it has to be a multiple of the interference spatial period and be smaller than the laser beam diameter ($\sim 18\%$ of the Gaussian intensity distribution),
- (2) the pulse to pulse overlap in the direction parallel to the line-like pattern has a strong influence on the structure depth; samples treated with high overlaps present a better texture homogeneity,
- (3) the Kurtosis (*Rku*) values cannot be used strictly to quantify homogeneity but they can provide an idea of the kind of topographic profile; samples with *Rku* values corresponding to a sinus shape (~ 1.5) have in general a high surface homogeneity.

Fig. 10. Kurtosis (Rku) along the roughness profiles produced by nanosecond DLIP on Ti6Al4V in the line-like pattern in relation with the fluence change, using the spatial periods of $\Lambda = 7.20 \mu\text{m}$ in the hatch distances of (a) $43.20 \mu\text{m}$ and (b) $28.80 \mu\text{m}$, $\Lambda = 5.82 \mu\text{m}$ in the hatch distances of (c) $40.74 \mu\text{m}$ and (d) $29.10 \mu\text{m}$ and $\Lambda = 4.31 \mu\text{m}$ in the hatch distances of (e) $43.10 \mu\text{m}$ and (f) $25.86 \mu\text{m}$. The overlap values of the pulse distribution were varied in 90.0%, 96.6%, 98.0% and 98.5%. The continuous line is just to guide the eye.

In our work, the most homogeneous DLIP microstructures were achieved using a spatial period of $5.82 \mu\text{m}$ with a hatch distance of $29.10 \mu\text{m}$, revealing *Surf Err%* values lower than 21%.

The here presented processing strategy is of significant relevance to assure in the future a certain performance over the whole treated area. In addition, the used parameters for the quantitative characterization of the surface texture homogeneity could be fundamental in relevant industrial processes, especially for quality management.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optlastec.2018.05.044>.

References

- [1] A.Y. Vorobyev, C. Guo, Direct femtosecond laser surface nano/microstructuring and its applications, *Laser Photon. Rev.* 7 (3) (2013) 385–407.
- [2] B.N. Chichkov, C. Momma, S. Nolte, F. Alvensleben, A. Tünnermann, Femtosecond picosecond and nanosecond laser ablation of solids, *Appl. Phys. A* 63 (1996) 109–115.
- [3] D.V. Ta, A. Dunn, T.J. Wasley, R.W. Kay, J. Stringer, P.J. Smith, C. Connaughton, J. D. Shephard, Nanosecond laser textured superhydrophobic metallic surfaces and their sensing applications, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 357 (2015) 248–254.
- [4] B.H. Lou, P.W. Shum, Z.F. Zhou, K.Y. Li, Preparation of hydrophobic surface on steel by patterning using laser ablation process, *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 204 (2010) 1180–1185.
- [5] D. Huerta-Murillo, A.I. Aguilar-Morales, S. Alamri, J.T. Cardoso, R. Jagdheesh, A. F. Lasagni, J.L. Ocaña, Fabrication of multi-scale periodic surface structures on Ti-6Al-4V by direct laser writing and direct laser interference patterning for modified wettability applications, *Opt. Lasers Eng.* 98 (2017) 134–142.
- [6] V.D. Ta, A. Dunn, T.J. Wasley, J. Li, R.W. Kay, J. Stringer, P.J. Smith, E. Esentruk, C. Connaughton, J.D. Shephard, Laser textured superhydrophobic surfaces and their applications for homogeneous spot deposition, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 365 (2016) 153–159.
- [7] P. Wagner, R. Fürstner, W. Barthlott, C. Neinhuis, Quantitative assessment to the structural basis of water repellency in natural and technical surfaces, *J. Exp. Bot.* 54 (385) (2003) 1295–1303.
- [8] M. Duarte, A. Lasagni, R. Giovanelli, J. Narciso, E. Louis, F. Mücklich, Increasing lubricant film lifetime by grooving periodical patterns using laser interference metallurgy, *Adv. Eng. Mat.* 10 (6) (2008) 554–558.
- [9] S. Schlie, E. Fadeeva, A. Korolova, A. Ovsianikov, J. Koch, A. Ngezhahayo, B.N. Chikov, Laser-based nanoengineering of surface topographies for biomedical applications, *Photonic. Nanostruct. – Fund. Appl.* 9 (2011) 159–162.
- [10] C. Zwahr, D. Günther, T. Brinkmann, N. Gulow, S. Oswald, M.G. Holthaus, A. Lasagni, Laser surface patterning of titanium for improving the biological performance of dental implants, *Adv. Healthc. Mater.* (2017) 1600858.
- [11] J. Chen, J.P. Ulerich, E. Abelev, A. Fasasi, C.B. Arnold, W.O. Soboyejo, An investigation of the initial attachment and orientation of osteoblast-like cells on laser grooved Ti-6Al-4V surfaces, *Mat. Sci. Eng. C29* (2009) 1442–1452.
- [12] D.A. Del Cerro, G.R.B.E. Römer, A.J. Huis in't Veld, Picosecond laser machined designed patterns with anti-ice effect, in: Proc. of the 11th International Symposium on Laser Precision Microfabrication, 2010.
- [13] R. Helbig, D. Günther, J. Fiedrichs, F. Rößler, A. Lasagni, C. Wermer, The impact of structure dimensions on initial bacterial adhesion, *Biomater., Sci.* 4 (2016) 1074–1078.
- [14] B. Raillard, J. Rémond, E. Ramos-Moore, N. Souza, C. Gachot, F. Mücklich, Wetting properties of steel surfaces modified by laser interference metallurgy, *Adv. Eng. Mater.* 15 (2013) No.5.
- [15] L. Gao, W. Zhou, Y. Wang, S. Wang, B. Chong, S. Li, Y. Liang, Fabrication of hydrophobic structures on stent by direct three-beam laser interference lithography, *Optik* 127 (2016) 5211–5214.
- [16] Y. Hu, Z. Wang, Z. Weng, M. Yu, D. Wang, Bio-inspired hierarchical patterning of silicon by laser interference lithography, *Appl. Opt.* 55 (12) (2016) 3226–3232.
- [17] S. Alamri, A.I. Aguilar-Morales, A. Lasagni, Controlling the wettability of polycarbonate substrates by producing hierarchical structures using direct laser interference patterning, *Eur. Polym. J.* 99 (2018) 27–37.
- [18] A. Rosenkranz, M. Hans, C. Gachot, A. Thome, S. Bonk, F. Mücklich, Direct laser interference patterning: tailoring of contact area for frictional and antibacterial properties, *Lubricants* 4 (2016) 2.
- [19] S. Heilman, C. Zwahr, A. Knape, J. Zschetzche, A.F. Lasagni, U. Füssel, Improvement of electrical conductivity between electrode and sheet in spot welding process by direct laser interference patterning, *Adv. Eng. Mat.* (2018) 1700755.
- [20] L.R.X. Cortella, I.A. Cestari, D. Guenther, A.F. Lasagni, I.N. Cestari, Endothelial cell responses to castor oil-based polyurethane substrates functionalized by direct laser ablation, *Biomed. Mater.* 12 (2017) 065010.
- [21] F. Rößler, K. Günther, A.F. Lasagni, In-volume structuring of a bilayered polymer foil using direct laser interference patterning, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 440 (2018) 1166–1171.
- [22] V. Lang, A. Rank, A.F. Lasagni, Large area one-step fabrication of three-level multiple-scaled micro and nanostructured nickel sleeves for roll-to-roll hot embossing, *Adv. Eng. Mater.* (2017) 1700126.
- [23] T. Tavera, N. Pérez, A. Rodríguez, P. Yurrita, S.M. Olaizola, E. Castaño, Periodic patterning of silicon by direct nanosecond laser interference ablation, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 258 (2011) 1175–1180.
- [24] A. Rodríguez, M. Echeverría, M. Ellman, N. Perez, Y.K. Verevkin, C.S. Peng, T. Berthou, Z. Wang, I. Ayerdi, J. Savall, S.M. Olaizola, Laser interference lithography for nanoscale structuring of materials: from laboratory to industry, *Microelectron. Eng.* 86 (2009) 937–940.
- [25] M. Bieda, E. Beyer, A. Lasagni, Direct fabrication of hierarchical microstructures on metals by means of direct laser interference patterning, *J. Eng. Mater. Technol.* 132 (2010) 031015-1.
- [26] L.E. Scriven, C.V. Sterling, The Marangoni effects, *Nature* 187 (1960) 186–188.
- [27] J.M. Drezet, S. Pellerin, C. Bezencon, S. Mokadem, Modelling the Marangoni convection in laser heat treatment, *J. Phys. IV.* 120 (2004) 299–306.
- [28] V.N. Moiseyev, *Titanium Alloys: Russian Aircraft and Aerospace Applications*, CRC Press, Florida, 2006.
- [29] W.J. Askeland, D.R. Fulay, P.P. Wright, *The Science and Engineering of Materials*, sixth ed., Cengage learning, Stamford, 2010.
- [30] S.M. Dubravka, B.R. Bojan, M.G. Biljana, B. Dimitri, D.M. Milos, S.T. Milan, Surface morphology modifications of titanium based implant induced by 40 picosecond laser pulses at 266nm, *J. Alloys Compd.* 501 (2010) 89–92.
- [31] J.M. Liu, Simple technique for measurements of pulsed Gaussian-beam spot sizes, *Opt. Lett.* 7 (5) (1982).
- [32] M. Bieda, M. Siebold, A. Lasagni, Fabrication of sub-micron surface structures on copper, stainless steel and titanium using picosecond laser interference patterning, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 387 (2016) 175–182.
- [33] A.I. Aguilar-Morales, S. Alamri, A. Lasagni, Micro-fabrication of high aspect ratio periodic structures on stainless steel by picosecond direct laser interference patterning, *J. Mater. Process. Tech.* 252 (2018) 313–321.
- [34] W. Steen, *Laser Material Processing*, Springer, London, 2010.
- [35] M.K. Khalaf, H.F. Al-Taay, A.S. Ali, Effect of radio frequency magnetron sputtering power on structural and optical properties of Ti6Al4V thin films, *Photon. Sens.* 7 (2) (2017) 163–170.
- [36] P.B. Johnson, R.W. Christy, Optical constants of transition metals: Ti V, Cr, Mn, Fe Co, Ni, and Pd., *Phys. Rev. B* 9 (12) (1974) 5056–5070.
- [37] ISO 4287 1997 Geometrical product specifications (GPS), Surface Texture: Profile Method-Terms, Definitions and Surface Texture Parameters (International Organization for Standardization).
- [38] A. Forbes, P. Tomlins, E. Gurdak, M. Ilseley, S. James, E. James, Methodologies for assessing local surface texture features that are relevant to cell attachment, *J. Mater. Sci. Med.* 21 (2010) 2463–2477.
- [39] M. Vadali, C. Ma, N.A. Duffie, X. Li, F.E. Pfefferkorn, Pulsed laser micro polishing: surface prediction model, *J. Manuf. Process.* 14 (2012) 307–315.
- [40] D.J. Biau, In brief: standard deviation and standard error, *Clin. Orthop. Relat. Res.* 469 (2011) 2661–2664.
- [41] M.G. Bulmer, *Principles of Statistics*, Dover, New York, 1979.
- [42] P.H. Westfall, Kurtosis as Peakedness, 1905–2014, *R.I.P. Am. Stat.* 68 (3) (2014) 191–195.
- [43] K.P. Balanda, H.L. Mac Gillivray, Kurtosis: a critical review, *J. Am. Stat. Assoc.* 42 (2) (1988) 111–119.
- [44] V.Y. Balandin, R. Niedrig, O. Bostanjoglo, Simulation of transformations of thin metal films heated by nanosecond laser pulses, *J. Appl. Phys.* 77 (1) (1995) 135–142.
- [45] M. D'Alessandria, A. Lasagni, F. Mücklich, Direct micro-patterning of aluminum substrates via laser interference metallurgy, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 255 (2008) 3210–3216.
- [46] V. Furlan, M. Biondi, A.G. Demir, G. Pariani, B. Previtali, A. Bianco, Sub-micro surface texturing of AZ31 Mg-alloy through two-beam direct laser interference patterning with a ns-pulsed green fiber laser, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 423 (2017) 619–629.
- [47] C. Rainieri, G. Fabbrocino, in: *Operational Modal Analysis of Civil Engineering Structures*, Springer, New York, 2014, p. 245.

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